

Improving electricity demand growth estimation in rural mini-grids through data-driven appliance diffusion modeling

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ABSTRACT

Accurate load modeling is crucial for designing reliable and cost-effective mini-grids in rural, under-served communities accessing electricity for the first time. Current models often fail to capture the evolving energy demands associated with changes in appliance ownership and socio-economic growth. The study introduces a bottom-up, adaptable model that forecasts a progressive appliance adoption and customer base in order to improve long-term electricity demand estimations. This study employs real-world appliance adoption trends from rural Kenya as a case study and uses logistic diffusion and optimization techniques to model appliance diffusion. The findings highlight significant variability in appliance adoption rates already during the first years of electricity access between different household groups, identified through clustering algorithms. This variability underscores the need for dynamic modeling over traditional static categorization of end users to more accurately reflect evolving consumer energy consumption profiles. The proposed model serves as a tool to enhance multiyear load profile generation and support microgrid design in similar settings.

Introduction

State of the art

Accurate demand forecasting is critical for designing cost-effective and reliable off-grid renewable energy systems for rural communities (Colombo, Crevani, Stevanato, & Mereu, 2024). As underserved communities transition from no electricity to full modern energy access, significant changes in the socio-economic landscape, as well as in the energy demand, are expected (Opiyo, 2020; Riva, Tognollo, Gardumi, & Colombo, 2018; Sayani et al., 2023). Yet, the scarcity of measured data on how electricity demand changes over time (Fillol et al., 2023; Fioriti et al., 2023; González-Torres, Pérez-Lombard, Coronel, Maestre, & Paolo, 2022), coupled with significant uncertainties and socio-economic complexities, makes it difficult to reliably forecast current and future demand (Blodgett, Dauenhauer, Louie, & Kickham, 2017; Sayani et al., 2023). Furthermore, the lack of modeling tools that effectively take into account load growth in mini-grid (MG) sizing, along with the limited accessibility of many energy models due to their proprietary or closed-source nature, remains a notable gap in the literature (Stevanato et al., 2020; Wassie & Ahlgren, 2023).

A review of forecasting methods highlights bottom-up approaches as particularly well suited for settings with rapid technological advancement, such as those in developing regions (Swan & Ugursal, 2009). In bottom-up modeling, several studies have developed archetypal user profiles that are useful for estimating demand when data are limited (Adeoye & Spataru, 2019; Falchetta et al., 2021; Stevanato, Sangiorgio, Mereu and Colombo, 2023). When data are available from comparable communities, comparative methods are often used (Allee, Williams, Davis, & Jaramillo, 2021).

Residential users' consumption classes have traditionally been defined by static appliance ownership (Ashetehe, Shewarega, Gessesse, Biru, & Lakeou, 2024; Falchetta et al., 2021; Stevanato, Sangiorgio, Mereu et al., 2023). However, appliance ownership evolves over time (Tomas Fillol, Pinomaa, Stevanato, Mereu, & Honkapuro, 2025), especially among households newly gaining access to electricity and starting with few or no appliances. Arguably, these classification approaches present limitations, as households would likely shift between classes as they gradually acquire new appliances, consequently failing to capture the evolution of demand. Despite appliance diffusion and an increasing number of connections being significant drivers

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of demand growth (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GmbH, 2016), they are often overlooked in most studies (Stevanato et al., 2025).

Scientific literature offers few examples with empirical historical data (Faraji, Hashemi-Dezaki, & Ketabi, 2020; Fobi, Deshpande, Ondiek, Modi, & Taneja, 2018; Hartvigsson, Ehnberg, Ahlgren, & Molander, 2021; Opiyo, 2020), that illustrate the growth of electricity demand among first-time electricity users. A study on a Tanzanian MG showed a significant increase in electricity purchases over a 30-month period (Hartvigsson et al., 2021). Similarly, a six-year longitudinal study of utility customers in Kenya detected a sharp initial demand increase, followed by slower growth and varied consumption patterns among customers that did not necessarily increase at a constant rate (Fobi et al., 2018). While these latter studies effectively demonstrate an increase in energy use following access to electricity, they often overlook the drivers behind demand shifts and their possible long-term impacts.

Annual growth is often substantial (Faraji et al., 2020) and long-term demand variations significantly impact system costs, more than fluctuations in daily load profiles (Riva, Gardumi, Tognollo and Colombo, 2019). Thus, recent studies emphasize integrating demand growth into forecasting models as a means to size energy systems more effectively while meeting the projected developmental needs (Parzen et al., 2023; Petrelli, Fioriti, Berizzi, Bovo, & Poli, 2021). Some studies have explored demand evolution by applying the concept of “electricity mobility”, which refers to “a household’s ability to expand its electricity use, either by increasing the number of electrical appliances they own or by using existing appliances more frequently” (Monyei, Oyedele, Akinade, Ajayi, Ezugwu et al., 2019). The study (Monyei, Oyedele, Akinade, Ajayi and Luo, 2019) highlights the importance of considering electricity mobility in policy design and critiques off-grid models that assume low and static demand. While a detailed examination of anticipated growth trajectories is beyond the scope of the aforementioned study, it could be argued that supporting such growth effectively requires a comprehensive understanding of how demand is likely to evolve and which drivers determine it.

Leveraging the concept of customer transitions between energy demand categories, (Namaganda-Kiyimba, Mutale, & Azzopardi, 2021) introduced a method for year-by-year load estimation using Markov chains. A key advantage of this approach lies in its integration of socio-economic characteristics, providing a context-aware framework. It captures customer mobility through shifts in consumption categories, driven by appliance ownership potential. The drawback of this approach is that it is not suitable for long-term forecasting, as it requires annual data to determine next year’s demand. Another study (Few et al., 2022) introduced a framework for demand estimation and solar MG design, using an appliance tier system derived from the Multi-tier Framework (MTF) of the World Bank (Bhatia & Angelou, 2015). The study presents scenarios based on different tier evolution paths, projecting residential demand by estimating the yearly share of households reaching each energy access tier. However, these scenarios rely on assumptions aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 7 target of universal energy access by 2030, which may not fully reflect real-world conditions. Similarly, other studies rely on hypothetical growth rates to estimate future demand (Few et al., 2022; Stevanato et al., 2020). In related research, the load growth was modeled as a function of household appliance ownership, applying the Bass model for innovation diffusion (Sayani et al., 2023). Appliance diffusion was also modeled in Riva, Gardumi et al. (2019), where a bottom-up model for local electricity demand in rural India was introduced, using survey data and empirical correlations. Although limited to their specific contexts, these latter studies make valuable contributions to demand evolution research while integrating socio-economic aspects into the modeling.

As observed, although there are numerous demand modeling frameworks in the scientific literature, current models still struggle to accurately forecast demand (Riva, Gardumi et al., 2019). It was found that

a common limitation of prevailing models for forecasting demand is their lack of integration of new connection projections, furthermore, most of the studies rely on arbitrary growth rates (Few et al., 2022; Stevanato et al., 2020). Additionally, variations in local dynamics hinder the generalization of findings across diverse socio-economic contexts (Rao & Ummel, 2017). Improving data availability and developing more accurate load evolution models are therefore essential to effectively integrate bottom-up methods for modeling dynamic electricity demand (Stevanato et al., 2025). There is a clear need for demand forecasting models that (i) reflect appliance diffusion over time, (ii) integrate growth in connections, and (iii) remain accessible and adaptable to various local contexts.

Contribution and organization of the paper

To address the identified gaps, this study investigates appliance diffusion trends during the first five years after households have connected to an MG in rural Kenya and assesses the evolution in the number of connections over time. Using these intermediate results, this study proposes a model designed to support realistic load growth scenarios by estimating the evolution of appliance ownership over a 20-year period and integrating a progressive number of MG connections. This bottom-up modeling approach, grounded in empirical data, enables the characterization of dynamic load profiles, providing a robust basis for generating future demand scenarios in comparable contexts. A dynamic approach to defining consumer classes is proposed. Rather than confining households to a fixed class, residential classes are defined by the rate of appliance acquisition, and hence, their appliance ownership is a dynamic attribute. The open-source modeling software RAMP (Lombardi et al., 2024) has been identified as an effective tool to simulate load demand based on appliance ownership, and it can adequately serve the proposed multiyear analysis. RAMP is particularly valuable for generating synthetic data in the absence of metered data, such as in remote regions (Lombardi, Balderrama, Quoilin, & Colombo, 2019). This makes the tool suitable for translating the appliance ownership output from our model into detailed multiyear load profiles.

While previous models have been developed for comparable purposes, they often fail to incorporate real-world data on how appliance ownership and energy demands evolve over time. Thus, a key contribution of this study is the development of a bottom-up forecasting model based on time series empirical data on appliance diffusion—a resource that is notably scarce for remote areas of the Global South (Fioriti et al., 2023). While it is recognized that predicting electricity demand requires a case-specific approach, the objective here is to propose a model that is straightforward to implement, adaptable to various scenarios through the adjustment of key parameters, and serves as a reference framework for appliance adoption modeling.

The following research questions are addressed in the present study:

- (1) What distinct patterns of appliance acquisition emerge during the first five years of electrification?
- (2) How can yearly new connections be effectively incorporated into the analysis of the growth of electricity demand?
- (3) How can these identified patterns be leveraged to forecast the evolution of electricity demand over a 20-year period?

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section “Data collection and processing” presents the data collection and processing methods employed. Section “Model development and methodology” explains the methodology and model development. The results are presented in Section “Results” and discussed further in Section “Discussion”. Finally, Section “Conclusions” provides the conclusions drawn along with practical recommendations for future research avenues.

Data collection and processing

A comprehensive survey of the Faza MG, located on Pate Island in Faza, Kenya, was conducted. The MG operates on a diesel generator with an installed capacity of 0.9 MW. A questionnaire was used to collect data at household level. Prior to the survey implementation, all required research licenses and permissions for survey data collection in Kenya were obtained, including a permit from the local chief, as required in Faza. Site mapping was conducted with mini-grid operators and local guides via phone and virtual meetings, and four project team members were trained as enumerators on the questionnaire procedures and ethical protocols. During the field campaign, participants were informed of the study's purpose and their right to skip questions or withdraw at any time. They were selected based on their expressed willingness to participate and were interviewed only after providing consent. To ensure confidentiality, all responses were anonymized. The authors of this study were responsible for survey design and provided overall supervision to ensure data quality. Field data collection activities — including enumerator coordination and logistical organization — were carried out under LEAP-RE program by the authors of the publication (Stevanato, Sangiorgio, Baldelli et al., 2023). The publication (Stevanato, Sangiorgio, Baldelli et al., 2023) documents the data collection process in detail and offers guidelines for similar survey implementations.

The data collection took place in February 2023. The survey included 192 mini-grid residential customers, with one respondent per household. For this study, only the households with at least five years of connection and complete questionnaire data were considered, resulting in a sample of 150 households. The sample size was determined using the Bukhari sample size formula, chosen to optimize sampling effort while aligning with project budget and timeline constraints, as explained in Stevanato, Sangiorgio, Baldelli et al. (2023).

The survey was conducted at a single point in time and collected retrospective data on appliance ownership. Respondents reported how many months or years ago each appliance they owned was purchased, in addition, they reported the year of connection to the MG. Based on the connection year, we calculated the number of years that had elapsed between the connection and the acquisition of each appliance. This enabled us to reconstruct appliance ownership year by year since electrification for each household. For example, a household connected in 2019 that acquired light bulbs in 2019, a fan in 2020, and a blender in 2022 was recorded as owning only light bulbs in year 1; light bulbs and a fan in years 2 and 3; and light bulbs, a fan, and a blender in year 4. This way, the data were organized into a time-series format. We applied year-level resolution, assuming respondents could reliably recall the acquisition year, even if the exact month was uncertain. Subsequently, for each year after connection, households were assigned an appliance tier based on the definitions outlined in Tomas Fillol et al. (2025), using a framework adapted from Bhatia and Angelou (2015) and Muza (2021), as illustrated in Fig. 1. The survey also gathered detailed data on appliance typical usage time slots, demographic information, the presence of solar home systems, and information about the establishment of income-generating activities. More questionnaire details can be found in the supplementary material.

Model development and methodology

The model development follows a two-step approach. The first step involves a detailed analysis of empirical data to establish baseline inputs for the model (Fig. 2:A and B). This provides the foundation for accurately capturing prevailing trends in appliance adoption patterns and tracking annual new MG connections. The next step involves developing a framework to forecast long-term appliance diffusion and customer aggregation (Fig. 2:C), based on the insights gained from the empirical data analysis step. Fig. 2:D and E illustrate the potential integration of appliance diffusion outputs with existing supply-side

Tier	Appliances			
	Lighting and mobile phones	Entertainment, office and fans	Cooking and clothes iron	Energy intensive appliances
1	Green	Red	Red	Red
2	Green	Green	Red	Red
3	Green	Green	Yellow (1)	Red
4	Green	Green	Yellow (<2 & 3)	Yellow (1 & 0)
5	Green	Green	Green	Green

The number of appliances is not limited
X The number of appliances is limited to X
 None of the appliances

Fig. 1. Appliance tier framework (Tomas Fillol et al., 2025).

electrification models for load simulation and system optimization, respectively. However, this study focuses on implementing the first three modules (Fig. 2:A, B, and C) of the proposed model. Thus, first, a logistic growth model is employed to predict future overall diffusion trends, represented by the average annual tier in each customer group. This is followed by an optimization procedure using Sequential Least Squares Programming (SLSQP) to estimate the specific share of households reaching appliance tiers every year since their connection. Lastly, to consider all the customer cohorts connecting in different years of the MG lifespan, the number of households in each tier is aggregated across all customer cohorts. Hence, the model output consists of the aggregated number of households in each appliance tier over a 20-year period.

Empirical data analysis

This section provides an overview of the steps taken to analyze the short-term empirical data.

Clustering of appliance uptake trends

To categorize users based on similar patterns of appliance uptake during the initial years of connection to the MG, the empirical annual variation in appliance tier is analyzed using clustering algorithms. Given that each clustering algorithm defines optimal clusters differently and has its own limitations, two approaches are tested: K-means clustering and agglomerative hierarchical clustering (HC). This dual approach reduces potential algorithm biases and strengthens the robustness of the results (Hennig, 2015; Mergulhão, Capra, Voglitsis, & Parikh, 2023). Both clustering algorithms were applied to empirical time series data tracking the appliance tier evolution of each household over the first five years of MG connection. For both algorithms, the number of clusters (K) was varied from 2 to 6, producing five solutions for each method. This resulted in a total of ten customer segmentation solutions based on similar appliance uptake patterns.

The validation of the clustering solutions is performed using a strategy adapted from Mergulhão et al. (2023), Sause, Gribov, Unwin, and Horn (2012) and Nguyen, Nowell, Bodner, and Obafemi-Ajayi (2018), which integrates quantitative methods with a qualitative oversight to ensure a thorough evaluation of the clustering outcomes (Nguyen et al., 2018). Typically, quantitatively identifying the optimal clustering solution involves using a single Clustering Validation Index (CVI), i.e., Silhouette (Sil). However, these indices have inherent biases that may not align with the specific context of the analysis (Akhanli & Hennig, 2020). Thus, the ensemble ranking system composed of different CVIs (Nguyen et al., 2018; Sause et al., 2012) is chosen. The ensemble includes the Davies–Bouldin (DB) index, Sil index, and Dunn index. Together, these indices provide a more comprehensive assessment of cluster quality. Each solution is ranked from 1 to 10 based on CVI

Fig. 2. Workflow of the proposed model for estimating long-term appliance diffusion. A: Input data; B: Empirical data analysis; C: Long-term appliance diffusion model; D: The long-term appliance diffusion output is designed to be fed into energy modeling tools, such as RAMP, to obtain multiyear electricity demand over a 20-year period; E: The RAMP output is then fed into mini-grid system optimization models, such as MicroGrids.Py, to optimize system sizing and dispatching strategies.

values, with final ranks determined by their cumulative scores. The top two are then qualitatively evaluated to select the most suitable solution.

Once the customers are segmented into clusters, the following information is derived for each cluster and for each of the first five years after MG connection (short-term): (1) the annual average appliance tier of all customers in the given cluster and (2) the percentage of households in each specific tier, referred to as yearly tier distribution. For the latter, a vector, $\mathbf{P}(t)$, is defined, whose components, $p_i(t)$, represent the share of customers in each tier i for a given year (t) , and their values change annually, reflecting the dynamic progression of households across tiers over time. The vector $\mathbf{P}(t)$ can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{P}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} p_1(t) \\ p_2(t) \\ p_3(t) \\ p_4(t) \\ p_5(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

Both the algorithms and validation techniques were implemented using the Scikit-Learn Python library (Pedregosa et al., 2011) with all parameters set to their default values (Scikit-learn, 0000).

Yearly new connections

To reflect the progressive nature of connections that align with real-world project dynamics, the annual number of new connections was derived from our empirical data. In this study, these yearly new connections define customer cohorts, which consist of households that connect to the MG in the same year. The process of customer aggregation by year and tier is explained in the following subsection.

Long-term appliance diffusion framework

With the short-term appliance tier diffusion patterns for each cluster already established, the next step involves estimating the appliance diffusion patterns for the following 15 years. The clustering results serve as input data for these projections. Subsequently, all the customer cohorts identified are aggregated by tiers over a 20-year period. To accomplish this, the steps outlined below were followed.

Logistic diffusion model to project tier growth trends

A logistic diffusion function is used to model the appliance growth trajectories for each cluster. Logistic growth models are commonly used to model the gradual adoption and eventual saturation of technologies or appliances in societies (Li, Chang, Zuo, & Zhang, 2023; McNeil & Letschert, 2010). The annual average appliance tier of each customer group, derived from the clustering step (Section “Clustering of appliance uptake trends”, output 1), serves as the basis for a 20-year projection. The model leverages observed diffusion dynamics from the initial five years to estimate future 15-year trends. Assuming that appliance adoption follows an S-shaped trajectory, as supported by the literature (Riva, Colombo and Piccardi, 2019), the function is defined by the following equation:

$$\bar{T}_{\text{logis}}(t) = \frac{L}{1 + e^{-b(t-t_0)}}, \quad (1)$$

where:

- $\bar{T}_{\text{logis}}(t)$ is the value of the logistic function at a given year (t) , representing the average predicted tier of all the customers in a specific customer group or cluster;
- L represents the asymptotic maximum value of the function, which corresponds to the maximum attainable tier. This value will be tested at tier 5 and adjusted to lower levels in order to explore various possible scenarios;
- b is the logistic growth rate. The b values are different for each cluster, and they are obtained by fitting the curve to the short-term data;
- t_0 is the inflection point of the curve. It differs by cluster and is obtained by fitting the curve to the short-term data.

Optimization to project long-term appliance tier distribution

With the previous step, the average future tier of the households is obtained. Next, to obtain the tier distributions of households annually up to year 20, an optimization problem is formulated. The optimization goal is to determine the proportion of households in each tier annually so that their weighted average, $\bar{T}(t)$, aligns as closely as possible with the average tier value, $\bar{T}_{\text{logis}}(t)$, determined by the logistic growth function in the previous step. This is achieved by solving the optimization problem using the Sequential Least Squares Programming algorithm, applied separately to each cluster solution. As a result of the optimization, the annual tier distribution vectors $\mathbf{P}(t)$, up to year 20 (long-term) are determined.

In addition to minimizing the difference between $\bar{T}_{\logis}(t)$ and $\bar{T}(t)$, the objective function incorporates specific features to ensure that the forecast is realistic. To achieve this, two penalty terms are employed; the first is a smoothness penalty, S , that limits abrupt shifts in the distribution from one year to the next, promoting a gradual progression. The second penalty term consists of a balance penalty, B , that avoids overconcentration in any single tier and prevents extreme allocations by promoting a balanced distribution across all tiers each year. Furthermore, several constraints are needed to ensure logical transitions and feasible tier proportions. The SLSQP algorithm is well-suited for managing both equality and inequality constraints. The optimization is implemented using Python's SciPy library. The complete objective function is formulated as follows:

$$\min \left\{ \left(\bar{T}(t) - \bar{T}_{\logis}(t) \right)^2 + \alpha \cdot S(t) + \beta \cdot B(t) \right\}, \quad (2)$$

where:

- $\bar{T}(t)$ represents the resulting average tier for a particular year, t . It is calculated as the average of the values in the tier distribution vector $\mathbf{P}(t)$ as follows:

$$\bar{T}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^5 i \cdot p_i(t), \quad (3)$$

where:

– i represents the tier, and 5 is the maximum attainable tier.

- α and β are regularization coefficients that control the influence of the smoothness and balance penalties, respectively, and are both set to 0.02. These values are deliberately small to ensure that the regularization terms refine the solution without significantly altering the primary objective of minimizing $\left(\bar{T}(t) - \bar{T}_{\logis}(t) \right)^2$.
- $S(t)$ is the smoothness penalty, defined as:

$$S(t) = \sum_{i=1}^5 \left(p_i(t) - p_i(t-1) \right)^2, \quad (4)$$

- $B(t)$ is the balance penalty, calculated as:

$$B(t) = \sum_{i=1}^5 \left(p_i(t) - \mu \right)^2, \quad (5)$$

where:

– μ represents the average proportion of households across all tiers. It equals 0.2, representing a baseline where each of the five tiers contains 20% of the households.

The first constraint imposed is an equality constraint to ensure that the sum of the components of the tier distribution vector, $\mathbf{P}(t)$, equals 1. This is necessary because the components represent proportions of the total number of households and must therefore collectively take into account the entire population. This is formulated as follows:

$$\sum_{i=1}^5 p_i(t) = 1 \quad \forall t. \quad (6)$$

Inequality constraints are imposed to ensure that the proportion in tier 1 can only decrease or stay constant, while tier 5 can only increase or stay constant over the years, represented by Eqs. (7) and (8), respectively:

$$p_1(t+1) \leq p_1(t) \quad \forall t, \quad (7)$$

$$p_5(t+1) \geq p_5(t) \quad \forall t. \quad (8)$$

The final constraint guarantees that the proportions of customers in each tier are nonnegative:

$$p_i(t) \geq 0 \quad \forall t. \quad (9)$$

The optimization process begins with empirical data from year 5. The algorithm iteratively adjusts the distribution for the subsequent year until convergence is achieved. The resulting distribution then serves as the starting point for the next iteration, and the process is repeated for each year.

The optimization process is conducted independently for each cluster, and each cluster exhibits different values of the vector $\mathbf{P}(t)$. However, for the sake of simplicity within this section, a uniform notation $\mathbf{P}(t)$, is employed to represent the general form of the distribution vector across all clusters.

Once the components of $\mathbf{P}(t)$ for each cluster are determined annually — which represent the share of customers in each tier for a given cluster — the actual number of customers in each tier can be calculated by multiplying the number of customers in the cluster, n , by the corresponding vector $\mathbf{P}(t)$. This process is repeated for each customer cohort. The general expression for computing the vector representing the number of customers in each tier, $\mathbf{n}(t)$, in year t , is given by:

$$\mathbf{n}(t) = n \cdot \begin{bmatrix} p_1(t) \\ p_2(t) \\ p_3(t) \\ p_4(t) \\ p_5(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} n_1(t) \\ n_2(t) \\ n_3(t) \\ n_4(t) \\ n_5(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

Aggregating customers by year of connection and appliance tier over the MG lifespan

The second phenomenon to consider is the progressive number of connections of new customer cohorts. There are, at this point, two different dynamics at play that contribute to the number of customers in each tier each year, and thus, to effectively describe the aggregation of customers, a specific notation is introduced for each new cohort of customers, and then, a detailed explanation is given of the assumptions made and the aggregation process.

Customer categorization notation: The number of new connections each year, or customers in each cohort, is denoted by n^j . The identifier j is used to distinguish different customer cohorts, taking values from the set {a,b,c,d,e}, where each letter represents a distinct cohort. Here, 'a' represents the customers connected in the first year of the MG, and 'e' represents those connected in the fifth year, mapping out new connections for each of the initial five years of the MG operation.

To further distinguish the number of customers within each tier and year across all cohorts, a subscript is added to represent the tier, i , and append the year, (t) , to the notation. The year (t) refers to the year after the connection to the MG, from the customer's perspective. Thus, $n_i^j(t)$ specifies the number of customers from cohort j who are in tier i in year t after their connection. For example, $n_5^b(10)$ represents the number of customers from cohort b — those who connected in the second year of the MG — who are in tier 5 in year 10 after their connection to the MG.

Assumptions:

To calculate the aggregated number of annual connections, and distribute them across the different tiers, the assumptions outlined below are followed.

- For each year after the MG begins operating, the total number of new customers, n^j , is derived from the empirical data, as established in Section "Yearly new connections". Yearly new connections. Future modelers may directly adjust these specific values within the provided code as needed.
- It is assumed that all the target households will be connected within the first five years of the MG operation.

- Each cohort of new customers is distributed across the identified appliance growth clusters in proportions consistent with those observed in our sample, as detailed in Section “Clustering”. Clustering.
- Each cohort of new customers, n^j , is assumed to experience appliance tier growth in alignment with the values established in Section “Optimization”. Optimization.

Since the MG is projected to have a 20-year operational lifespan, not all customer cohorts will reach the 20-year mark on the growth trajectory. For example, customers connected in the first year, n^a , will complete the full 20-year progression. In contrast, customers connected in year 5, n^e , will only reach 15 years, ($t = 15$), on the growth trajectory by the end of the operational period of the MG.

Note that the total number of households in each cohort remains constant over time and is always equal to the sum of the households in each tier i , within that cohort, regardless of the year t being analyzed. This relationship can be represented as follows:

$$n^j = \sum_{i=1}^5 n_i^j(t) \quad \forall t, \quad (10)$$

where:

- n^j represents the number of connections in cohort j .
- $n_i^j(t)$ represents the number of households connected in cohort j that belong to tier i in year t after their connection.

Aggregation of customers by tier for each year from the perspective of the MG: Up to now, the focus has been on describing the appliance tier evolution from the customer’s perspective, using t to denote the time after their connection to the MG. However, the ultimate goal is to determine the number of customers in each appliance tier for each year of the MG lifespan. For this purpose, t_{mg} is introduced, representing the number of years since the MG started operating. From this point forward, this paper will clearly specify whether the time perspective being referred to is considered from the perspective of the customer or the MG, whenever necessary.

The total cumulative number of households connected up to each year is represented by $N(t_{\text{mg}})$. For instance, $N(t_{\text{mg}} = 1)$ equals n^a as only the first customer cohort has been connected at that point. The value of $N(t_{\text{mg}})$ changes during the first five years of the MG operation; thereafter, it remains constant, as no new connections are considered. The total number of households in a given tier i in year (t_{mg}), from the perspective of the MG, denoted as $n_i(t_{\text{mg}})$, is obtained by aggregating the customers in that tier across all customer cohorts connected up to that year. This aggregation can be expressed as follows:

$$n_i(t_{\text{mg}}) = \sum_{j \in \{a,b,c,d,e\}} n_i^j(t_{\text{mg}}) = n_i^a(t_{\text{mg}}) + n_i^b(t_{\text{mg}}) + n_i^c(t_{\text{mg}}) + n_i^d(t_{\text{mg}}) + n_i^e(t_{\text{mg}}) \quad (11)$$

Since not all customers are connected to the MG in the same year the MG is commissioned ($t_{\text{mg}} = 1$), the following conditions apply to the initial years of connection for every tier i :

$$\begin{aligned} n_i^b(t_{\text{mg}} = 1) &= 0 \\ n_i^c(t_{\text{mg}} \in \{1, 2\}) &= 0 \\ n_i^d(t_{\text{mg}} \in \{1, 2, 3\}) &= 0 \\ n_i^e(t_{\text{mg}} \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Table 1 provides a summary of the aggregation operations to obtain the cumulative number of customers in each appliance tier for each year of the MG.

Results

This section presents the results of implementing the proposed model for estimating long-term appliance diffusion.

Empirical data analysis

Empirical data are analyzed in this section to serve as inputs for the modeling framework. This includes the application of clustering algorithms to identify short-term appliance uptake trends and the examination of yearly new connections.

Clustering

Cluster analysis is conducted using the annual appliance tier across five years as the primary feature. By analyzing these temporal patterns, the households are classified into distinct groups that exhibit similar trajectories in appliance acquisition. Two clustering algorithms, K-Means and HC, are employed, with multiple cluster solutions tested for each method. The optimal clustering solution is identified through a combination of methods: quantitative validation metrics are applied to shortlist the two best-performing solutions, which are then subjected to a qualitative assessment to make the final decision.

Selection of best-performing solutions: The clustering solutions are evaluated quantitatively using the Sil score, DB index, and Dunn index, with ranks assigned for each metric; see **Table 2** for the results of the ensemble validation approach. The aggregated rank summarizes the performance across all metrics, where a higher rank indicates better overall clustering quality.

According to the ensemble validation, the top solutions are K-Means with two clusters and HC with three clusters, both achieving the highest aggregate ranks and final weighted ensemble scores. Thus, these two solutions are selected for further examination.

Comparison adoption trends by cluster: **Fig. 3** compares the average appliance tier over five years for the two clustering solutions: K-Means with $K = 2$ on the left and hierarchical clustering with $K = 3$ on the right. In the $K = 2$ K-Means solution, a clear distinction is observed between cluster 1 and cluster 2 in terms of appliance adoption pathways. Households in cluster 1 (integrated by 71% of the cluster’s households) exhibit a slow and limited increase in appliance ownership, starting with an average of tier 1 and reaching slightly above tier 2 after five years since the connection to the MG. In contrast, cluster 2 shows a significantly higher adoption rate, with households starting at an average of around tier 2 and steadily increasing to reach an average higher than tier 4 by year 5. In the hierarchical clustering solution with $K = 3$ (right panel), three clusters are presented. Cluster 1, covering 69% of the households, remains consistent with its analogue cluster in the $K = 2$ solution, exhibiting a minimal growth in appliance adoption. Conversely, cluster 2, which accounts for 23% of the households, demonstrates a rapid and sustained increase in appliance ownership. Although this trend mirrors that of cluster 2 in the $K = 2$ solution, it is characterized by a lower initial starting point. However, cluster 3 exhibits a relatively flat adoption pattern, with the initial average already slightly exceeding tier 4 in the first connection year and a minor change in appliance ownership over time.

Socio-demographic characteristics of cluster membership: For the two preselected solutions, the key socio-demographic factors of households in each cluster are analyzed, including household income, age of the household head, number of rooms, number of income earners, education level, presence of a home-based business, and prior ownership of solar PV systems before MG connection. **Fig. 4** provides a comparison of these characteristics across clusters. **Fig. 4** shows the distribution of the values of each variable in letter-value plots, except for binary variables, which are presented in bar graphs. Letter-value plots resemble box plots but offer a more detailed view of the shape of the distribution. These plots start with the median as the centerline. Each successive layer outward covers half of the remaining data. Thus, the first two layers outside the median collectively represent 50% of the data, the next two layers account for 25%, and so on until the outlier level.

In the case of the hierarchical clustering solution with $K = 3$, there is clearly visible distinction between clusters, but the differences

Table 1
Cumulative connections and aggregation by tier from the perspective of the Mini-Grid.

t_{mg}^a	Cumulative connections ^b $N(t_{mg})$	Overview ^c $N(t_{mg})$	Households ^d Tier 1 $n_1(t_{mg})$...	Households ^d Tier 5 $n_5(t_{mg})$
1	$N(1) = n^a$	$N(1) = \sum_{i=1}^5 n_i^a(1)$	$n_1(1) = n_1^a(1)$...	$n_5(1) = n_5^a(1)$
2	$N(2) = n^a + n^b$	$N(2) = \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=a}^b n_i^j(2)$	$n_1(2) = \sum_{j=a}^b n_1^j(2)$...	$n_5(2) = \sum_{j=a}^b n_5^j(2)$
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
20	$N(20) = \sum_{j=a}^e n^j = n^a + n^b + n^c + n^d + n^e$	$N(20) = \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=a}^e n_i^j(20)$	$n_1(20) = \sum_{j=a}^e n_1^j(20)$...	$n_5(20) = \sum_{j=a}^e n_5^j(20)$

^a MG year, t_{mg} .

^b Cumulative number of household connections up to year t_{mg} , $N(t_{mg})$.

^c Overview of $N(t_{mg})$ composition: sum of households in all appliance tiers connected up to year t_{mg} .

^d Total number of households in appliance tier i in year t_{mg} , $n_i(t_{mg})$, aggregated across all connected cohorts.

Table 2
Validation of cluster solutions.

Algorithm	Sil (max)	DB (min)	Dunn (max)	Sil rank	DB rank	Dunn rank	Aggregated ranks	Final weighted ensemble
K-Means ($K = 2$)	0.6114	0.6905	0.2182	10	9	2	21	10
HC ($K = 3$)	0.5907	0.6932	0.2182	8	8	2	18	9
HC ($K = 2$)	0.6078	0.7094	0.1414	9	7	1	17	8
K-Means ($K = 4$)	0.5723	0.7177	0.2672	6	6	4	16	7
K-Means ($K = 3$)	0.5860	0.7191	0.2236	7	5	3	15	6
HC ($K = 6$)	0.5681	0.9448	0.3015	5	3	6	14	5
HC ($K = 4$)	0.5516	0.6748	0.2182	2	10	2	14	4
K-Means ($K = 6$)	0.5599	0.9993	0.3015	4	1	6	11	3
HC ($K = 5$)	0.5515	0.8235	0.2773	1	4	5	10	2
K-Means ($K = 5$)	0.5527	0.9683	0.2672	3	2	4	9	1

Fig. 3. Five years' cluster K-means ($K = 2$) on the left, HC ($K = 3$) on the right.

between clusters 2 and 3 are less pronounced. For example, while cluster 1 consistently exhibits a lower income and fewer rooms, clusters 2 and 3 show more overlap in characteristics such as income, number of rooms, education, age, business at home, and PV ownership.

In contrast, the $K = 2$ K-Means solution provides a more pronounced distinction between the two groups. In this solution, cluster 1 is characterized by households with a lower income, fewer rooms, fewer salaried individuals, and a smaller percentage of home businesses (approximately 25%) compared with cluster 2, where over 50% of the households operate home businesses. Additionally, the solar PV ownership before the MG connection is lower in cluster 1 (around 35%) compared with cluster 2 (over 50%). Furthermore, cluster 1 shows a higher proportion of households with lower education levels. In terms of age, cluster 1 exhibits an interquartile range (IQR) between 30 and the mid-50s, and cluster 2 presents an age IQR ranging from 30 to the mid-40s. Furthermore, cluster 1 covers a broader age range, including individuals at both extremes of the age spectrum—those in early adulthood and advanced age. This suggests that these age groups tend to adopt appliances more slowly compared with those in middle age.

Selection of clustering solution: While both solutions perform well based on the validation metrics, a qualitative analysis of the socio-demographic variables suggests that the $K = 2$ K-Means solution more effectively captures distinctions between household groups. Additionally, the small number of households in cluster 3 in the $K = 3$ HC solution, coupled with the fewer socio-demographic variables available to differentiate this cluster, leads to the conclusion that the K-means with $K = 2$ solution provides a more meaningful segmentation of the data. In this solution, cluster 1 represents the Late Adopter (LA) households, while cluster 2 corresponds to the Early Adopter (EA) households.

Annual distribution tiers across clusters

Fig. 5 illustrates the tier distribution over five years for the two different clusters of households: LA and EA. As expected, the LA cluster demonstrates slow progression, with most households remaining in the lower tiers over the five-year period. The majority of households in year 1 are in tier 1, with only a small percentage in tier 2. Over the following years, there is a slow tier progression toward higher tiers. By

Fig. 4. Cluster characteristics; K-Means ($K = 2$) on the top, HC ($K = 3$) on the bottom.

Fig. 5. Tier distribution over the first five years of connection to the MG.

year 5, more than 45% of the households are still in tier 1, although many have moved to tiers 2 and 3 and a small number to higher tiers. In contrast, the EA cluster shows much faster advancement and a wider distribution in year 1, with households spread across tiers 1 and 2, and a few already in tier 3. Over time, a more noticeable upward shift occurs as households move from lower tiers to higher ones. By year 5, all households have progressed to tiers 3, 4, or 5, with a significant proportion, about 40%, having reached tier 5.

Yearly new connections

Table 3 shows the proportion of annual connections obtained from the empirical data. It is observed that most connections take place in the first two years, followed by a gradual decline over time. It should be noted that the empirical data analysis is based on 150 households from the first three connection cohorts with complete 5-year data, serving as a representative sample for capturing appliance adoption dynamics during the initial years of MG operation. In contrast, the

proposed framework is designed to include five cohorts, reflecting that new connections continued for up to five years after the MG began operations. For simplicity, the simulation of long-term appliance adoption is scaled to 150 households in total. The choice of 150 households for the simulation is illustrative for this case study. In practice, the total number of households is a user-defined parameter, and the framework can readily accommodate different values. The relative distribution of households across cohorts, however, is set according to the empirical proportions.

Despite this early peak, it is notable that over 35% of connections were made after the third year, underscoring the value of considering a continued growth in the number of connected households, and, consequently, in demand. These inputs are important for understanding load evolution over time and can provide valuable insights for planning future expansion, which can be more cost-effective compared with a fixed-capacity system (Stevanato et al., 2020).

Fig. 6. Logistic diffusion functions to estimate average appliance tier trends.

Table 3
Number of new connections each year.

	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Proportion of connections relative to total target connections	28%	36%	18%	12%	6%
Number of connections (n^i) in our case study	$n^a = 42$	$n^b = 54$	$n^c = 27$	$n^d = 18$	$n^e = 9$

Logistic diffusion model

In the logistic growth function, the carrying capacity, L , represents the maximum attainable tier or saturation point of appliance ownership. In the EA cluster, the average tier in year 5 already exceeds 4, suggesting that within the subsequent 15 years, most households in this group could potentially reach tier 5. In contrast, for the LA households, after five years of being connected to the MG, the average tier only slightly exceeds tier 2. Given this slower progression and lacking strong evidence to suggest that all households will eventually reach tier 5, several alternative scenarios are proposed for testing by varying the maximum attainable average tier for this group. To guide the choice of scenarios, findings from a previous study in the Faza MG (Tomas Fillol et al., 2025) are taken into account. The study indicated that 70% of households with six years of electricity access already owned, on average, two high-tier appliances (tier 3 or 4). Such evidence suggests that continued growth beyond tier 3 is realistic, since reaching tier 3 requires only a single high-tier appliance. The study also reported customers’ intentions to purchase additional appliances in the future, for example, 52% expressed interest in refrigerators, 30% in ovens, 30% in blenders, and 30% in pressure cookers. These observations support the plausibility of scenarios in which average tiers exceed 3 after a period of 15 years. Accordingly, the trend of the LA group is explored under the following scenarios:

1. **High Uptake:** LA achieve the maximum attainable tier ($L = 5$).
2. **Moderate Uptake:** LA attain an average tier of 4.5 ($L = 4.5$).
3. **Low Uptake:** LA reach an average tier of 4 ($L = 4$).

Fig. 6 illustrates the logistic growth curves displaying the evolution of average appliance tiers within the identified clusters. The right graph displays the three different adoption scenarios for the LA group. The curves demonstrate how appliance ownership progresses over a 20-year period under each scenario, with empirical data points from the first five years plotted for comparison. The left graph represents the appliance tier trend for the EA group. The curve shows that the EA group quickly approaches the maximum tier level, with a high degree of fit to the empirical data, as indicated by the R^2 value of 0.99, the R^2 values for the LA being slightly lower, with values around 0.77 in every scenario.

Optimization

This step focuses on estimating the specific household’s tier distribution for the upcoming years. To achieve this, the SLSQP optimization method is employed, utilizing historical distribution data (years 1–5) and the logistic curve equation that represents the yearly target average tier for each customer group as the input. A single solution is presented for the EA group, whereas three distinct scenarios — high, moderate, and low uptake — are outlined for the LA group to take into account uncertainties in this group.

Fig. 7 illustrates the appliance tier distribution solutions. Each plot employs violin plots to display the distribution of users across appliance tiers over a 20-year period, with tiers ranging from 1 to 5 and the logistic curve employed for each case. In the top-left plot, the EA group shows a rapid initial increase in appliance tiers, stabilizing around tiers 4–5 by year 6. By year 13, over 90% of the households have reached tier 5, and this level remains nearly constant in the subsequent years. In contrast, the LA group with a high uptake, shown in the top-right plot, demonstrates a slower trend, with most users reaching tiers 4–5 by year 10 and over 80% reaching tier 5 by year 20. The bottom-left plot shows the LA with a moderate growth, with most users reaching mid-level tiers (around 3–4) by year 15 and around 55% achieving the highest tier by year 20. Lastly, the bottom-right plot represents the LA with a low uptake, where the adoption is limited; by year 20, most users remain within lower to mid-level tiers, with only 40% reaching the highest appliance tier.

Aggregation of annual connections growth

To demonstrate the functionality of the model, the low uptake scenario is used, which incorporates the LA trend for 71% of the customers and the EA trend for the remaining 29%. These trends are illustrated in the fourth and first plots of Fig. 7, respectively. Fig. 8 provides a visual representation of the cumulative number of households in each tier for our case study of 150 customers, illustrating the gradual increase and transition of customers across tiers over the 20-year period. The trend illustrates the increasing adoption of advanced appliances as customers gain more access and potentially more usage experience. For instance, in the first year, 35 customers are at tier 1, this is, $n_1(1) = 35$, while only 1 customer starts at tier 5, denoted as $n_5(1) = 1$. New customer connections were aggregated each year, reaching a peak in year 5, when the final cohort of customers was connected. At the end of year 20, it is projected that 56% of the customers will have reached tier 5, with the remaining customers distributed among the lower tiers. Fig. 8 represents the output of the proposed modeling framework, whose numerical results would serve as inputs for other electrification models, e.g., by employing tools such as RAMP followed by Microgrids.Py.

As a demonstration of the application of the proposed model to estimating the demand growth, aggregated demand was computed at five-year intervals using RAMP, employing the methodology outlined in Falchetta et al. (2021). Fig. 9 presents the evolution of aggregate load over time. The left panel presents the total average daily electricity

Fig. 7. Optimization results: tier distributions over a 20-year period.

Fig. 8. Aggregation of customers by tier and year.

Fig. 9. Projected demand growth for 150 households at five-year steps: Low uptake scenario.

demand, while the right panel shows the contribution of each tier to the overall demand. All the parameters used in constructing the aggregated demand are provided in [Tomas Fillol \(2025b\)](#). A more comprehensive analysis of demand dynamics and system optimization will be conducted in future work, building on the results presented in this study and following the workflow presented in [Fig. 2](#).

Discussion

This study reduces a significant gap in the limited data and understanding of the long-term growth in electricity demand in rural

households accessing electricity for the first time. The study demonstrates the logistic growth of appliance adoption through empirical data and employs the observed historical trends to formulate a novel modeling framework for long-term projections of household electricity demand based on appliance adoption.

The proposed framework incorporates two key demand growth factors: the expansion of the consumer base and the progressive adoption of electrical appliances by each consumer. By formulating a modeling framework that simulates these dynamics, this research introduces a novel approach to studying rural electrification. The model output,

calibrated on a Kenyan MG, provides a projection of the number of households in each appliance tier over 20 years. By integrating the model with existing stochastic energy demand models, such as RAMP, and subsequently incorporating the RAMP outputs into Microgrids.Py, this study presents an effective approach for simulating multiyear, user-driven energy demand and for planning sizing and dispatching strategies for MG projects in remote areas.

The empirical data analysis confirms that not all customers will experience the same organic growth pattern, as pointed out in Fobi et al. (2018). Clustering algorithms are employed to identify distinct customer categories based on their appliance adoption rates. Approximately 70% of the households are categorized as Late adopters. Early adopters generally feature households with higher incomes and educational levels, a higher number of households with business operations, and a higher prevalence of previous solar home system ownership than Late adopters.

The analysis reveals substantial differences in the appliances owned between the first and fifth years after the MG connection across both clusters. The model results indicate that even in scenarios of low uptake, there could be substantial variability in electricity demand over 20 years. For instance, while in year 5, more than 60% of the households are in the lowest appliance tiers (1 or 2), this proportion drops below 10% by year 20. Conversely, the proportion of users in the higher tiers (4 and 5) increases from about 30% in year 5 to approximately 80% by year 20. This underscores the importance of dynamic modeling over traditional static categorization to more accurately reflect the evolving profiles of consumer consumption. Off-grid electrification projects must therefore adopt measures that ensure availability, and adequacy of supply, which enable services comparable with those provided by the main grid and being capable of accommodating demand growth.

Furthermore, the provided codebase (Tomas Fillol, 2025a) enhances the adaptability of the framework, allowing for modifications to suit various scenarios. Inputs such as the total number of customers, the share of customers in each cluster group, and the scenario type are parameters that can be adjusted, providing a data-driven alternative to conventional energy modeling, which often relies on arbitrary trends. For instance, the model can be employed directly for comparable communities, thereby serving as a tool to enhance bottom-up demand forecasting and to support mini-grid planning in rural electrification projects. Moreover, the framework can be calibrated by replicating modules A, B, and C (Fig. 2), using input data that can be easily collected through local surveys. This also allows for customization of the appliance mix within each tier to reflect local contexts. Likewise, yearly new connection values, which might be difficult to generalize from a single system, could also be easily adjusted as needed.

Despite the notable scientific contributions in developing a data-driven model to enhance multiyear electricity demand estimations for off-grid rural electrification, this study also acknowledges certain limitations. The survey-based method, invaluable for capturing detailed and nuanced data, is subject to potential biases and inaccuracies. Furthermore, electricity prices may also influence appliance adoption; however, this study does not take into account the potential effects of different electricity tariff structures. Notably, Kenya employed a flat tariff system until 2023, after which the tariff structure was reformed (KPLC, 2023). Although electricity prices have generally exhibited an upward trend, price increases have historically been uniform across households. Assessing the influence of electricity tariffs on appliance adoption would require a dedicated analysis, supported by detailed household-level data capturing exposure to varying tariff regimes. Additionally, the case study approach limits the generalization of our findings; thus, in the future, replicating this study across various locations could reveal differences in adoption rates and would allow for the calibration of the model across diverse settings. The results of such replications could inform the broad application of this framework to enhance demand estimations across various locations.

We acknowledge that the cross-sectional design of this study constitutes a limitation, as it restricts the ability to observe household-level appliance adoption trajectories longitudinally. However, the aggregated trends observed here — such as widespread ownership of basic appliances and gradual progression to higher tiers — are consistent with previous studies (Muza & Debnath, 2021). Moreover, a previous study by the authors (Tomas Fillol et al., 2025), which applied an econometric analysis using current appliance tier and years since electrification (without reconstructing a full temporal trajectory), yielded consistent results. For example, households engaged in home businesses or equipped with solar home systems were more likely to reach higher tiers—an observation that is also found in the socio-demographic analysis of this study, where Early Adopters showed a higher proportion of such households. While this does not fully resolve the limitation, the convergence of findings across different studies and approaches provides a strong indication that the results are robust and meaningful.

Conclusions

The results of this study have practical implications. The proposed framework not only fulfills the primary purpose of estimating appliance adoption patterns in our case study but also serves as a tool for researchers and practitioners to analyze the progression of appliance uptake in similar settings.

The limitations presented in the discussion section are acknowledged as areas for future research to build upon. For future applications, annual monitoring to generate longitudinal data, allowing for more accurate tracking of connections, appliance adoption, and refinement of model parameters, is recommended. This would enable periodic updates to demand projections and support more flexible capacity expansion planning, rather than relying on a fixed capacity project. The model presented in this study offers a foundation for exploring potential demand growth scenarios, which can be updated over time through continuous monitoring. To strengthen reproducibility in future work, where longitudinal data or panel survey designs are not feasible, validating appliance ownership responses by interviewing multiple household members is recommended to enhance the accuracy of the results.

A potential research avenue involves integrating the proposed modeling approach into the monitoring and evaluation of new mini-grids, to enhance operational efficiency and guide business model adjustments that promote alignment with estimated demand. The authors emphasize that a central objective of this work is to provide a reference framework, supported by open-access code, that can be refined as new empirical evidence becomes available. Future research may extend this framework by considering additional drivers of long-term appliance adoption — such as microfinance programs, electricity tariffs, or supply reliability — which could substantially influence the trajectory of appliance uptake and usage among rural households.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Leticia Tomas Fillol: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nicolò Stevanato:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Antti Pinomaa:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Riccardo Mereu:** Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Samuli Honkapuro:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary data

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